

SPONDYLODISCITIS: MODERN APPROACHES TO TREATMENT

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Resume; restart. The goal of diabetes treatment is to eliminate the pathogen, restore and maintain the structure and function of the spine, smooth out neurological deficits, and relieve pain. Conservative therapy Conservative treatment, which is the standard of care, is indicated in the absence of lesions and spinal cord compression on CT and MRI. There is no disagreement on conservative methods of therapy, and currently it includes antibacterial, immunocorrective , detoxification therapy, physiotherapy and immobilization.

Treatment

Immobilization should be used when there is a risk of developing severe pain and spinal instability. Antibacterial therapy Early stages of diabetes are easy to treat with antibiotics. Immediate initiation of empiric antibiotic therapy is recommended in patients with hemodynamic compromise, sepsis, septic shock, or progressive or severe neurologic impairment. Antibiotics are prescribed intravenously in maximum therapeutic doses, in some cases intra-aortic administration of antibiotics is suggested. In other cases, the introduction of antibiotic therapy may be delayed until the biopsy results are obtained, because early initiation of empiric treatment leads to distortion of the biopsy results. Empirical therapy should cover the most common pathogens of diabetes and penetrate well into the central nervous system and bones. by opinion CE Chenoweth [et al.] (2010), I. Moraru (2012), T. Gouliouris [et al.] (2012), K. Zarghooni [et al. al .] (2013), in most cases, the following combination of antibiotics for empiric treatment is effective: 1. Preferred regimen: vancomycin 15-20 mg/kg + ceftriaxone 2 g - intravenously, every 12 hours 2. Alternative regimen for penicillin allergy : vancomycin 15-20 mg/kg + aztreonam 2 g - intravenously, every 8 hours. Medicines for the treatment of diabetes are included as part of empiric therapy: cefepime 6 g - intravenously, meropenem - daily. intravenous injection. If a pathogen is identified as a result of bacteriological studies, rational antibiotic therapy is prescribed, which is carried out taking into account the resistance of the isolated pathogen to antibacterial drugs. The duration of parenteral antibiotic therapy is on average 2-4 weeks and depends on the improvement of the clinical picture, the normalization or significant decrease of ESR and the number of leukocytes. The level of C-reactive protein can serve as a basis for switching from parenteral antibiotics to oral antibiotics . If this indicator normalizes in the first two weeks of treatment, it is recommended to switch from parenteral administration of antibiotics to oral

administration. Treatment should continue for at least 6-8 weeks after the symptoms of inflammation have normalized. According to many authors, the total duration of antibacterial therapy should be from 6 weeks to 3 months in the case of suppurative diabetes and up to 1 year in the case of tuberculosis etiology of the disease.

Surgical treatment

The goals of surgical intervention are to destroy the infectious focus, take a biopsy for microbiological and histological examination, decompress the spinal canal with stabilization and restoration of damaged spinal structures. Most of the authors (R. Sobottke [et al .] 2008, K. Zarguni [et al .] 2012, S. Mann [et al al .] 2004, RM Duarte , AR Vaccaro 2013) urgent surgery is recommended for the development of neurological deficits, as well as spinal instability and deformity. Absolute and relative indications for surgical treatment of diabetes are presented in Table 1. However, the relative indications for surgical treatment of diabetes in patients with pain and unresponsive to conservative treatment are still controversial. Compared to conservative therapy, surgical treatment helps relieve inflammation and pain more safely and quickly. Of course, the placement of fixation materials in the infected area can lead to their colonization and the continuation of the infection. If local antibiotics are used during the sanitation of the infected bone and surrounding tissues, there may be no complications after the installation of spinal structures. Titanium implants are recommended because they are associated with a lower recurrence rate. The issue of optimal surgical tactics for diabetes remains controversial. Surgical treatment of diabetes can be done in one or two stages. If there is a neurological defect, it is necessary to urgently decompress and stabilize the spine, because the dynamics of the development of neurological complications depends on the speed of surgical intervention. In patients without neurological deficits, but with comorbidities, a two-stage intervention is preferable. The second stage of the operation is performed one or two weeks after the first. The type of surgical intervention depends on the level of the lesion, the degree of destruction and the developed complications. In this case, in the first stage of the operation, damaged and necrotic tissues are removed by corporotransversectomy , discectomy or laminectomy . In the second stage, the supporting and protective functions of the spine are restored . After the period of immobilization, the patient is prescribed physiotherapy, ultrasound therapy, acupuncture and exercise therapy. Long-term restriction of physical activity leads to muscle

atrophy. The return to normal life is carried out gradually with an increase in the volume of load and movements;

Summary

The analysis of the literature showed that early diagnosis of diabetes remains a difficult task, while the disease requires timely adequate treatment with antibacterial drugs and control of their effectiveness. The approach to surgical treatment of diabetes in pain (the nature and intensity of pain) also remains controversial and not entirely clear, which requires further research.

Literature:

1. Nonspecific pyogenic spondylodiscitis: clinical presentation, surgical treatment and outcome in 24 patients / S. Mann [et al.] // Neurosurg . Attention. - December 2004. - vol. 17, N 6. – R. E 3.
2. 2018-03-22 Treatment of adult spontaneous spondylodiscitis and its reproduction / A. Sur [et al.] // Ann. R. Coll. Surg. English. - September 2015. - vol. 97, N 6. – P. 451–455.
3. Diagnosis and treatment of pyogenic osteomyelitis of the cervical spine in adults / FL Jr. Acosta [et al.] // Neurosurg . Attention. - December 2004. - vol. 17, N 6. – R. E 2.
4. Bacteriological characteristics of infectious spondylodiscitis in the Mohammed V military training hospital in Rabat / A. Zohoun [et al.] // Braz. J. Microbiol. - October-December 2012. - vol. 43, N 4. – B. 1327–1331.
5. Vertebral osteomyelitis, discitis and spinal epidural abscess in adults [Electronic resource]: guideline summary // Clearing guideline (NGC): [Website]. - August 2013. - Access: <https://www.guideline.gov/summaries/summary/47349/vertebral-osteomyelitis-discitis-and-spinalepidural-abscess-in-adults>. - Date of entry: 24.01.2018
6. Duarte, RM Spinal cord infection: modern and management algorithm / RM Duarte, AR Vaccaro // Eur. Spine J. - December 2013 . - vol . 22, N 12. – P. 2787–2799.
7. Ardashev, IP Vertebral infection / IP Ardashev, EI Ardasheva // Spinal surgery. - 2009. - No. 2. - P. 68-78.
8. Identification of the pathogen in suspected cases of pyogenic spondylodiscitis / AF Sheikh [et al.] // Front. Cell. Contagion. Microbiol. - March 2017. - vol. 7. - R. 60.

